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Research Article

**CROSS SECTIONAL COMPARATIVE STUDY TO EXPLORE
THE CURVE WIDTH IN UNTREATED CLASS II SUBJECTS
WITH NORMAL AND HIGH MANDIBULAR PLANE POINTS**¹Dr Waqar Qamar, ²Dr Arslan Arshad Satti, ³Dr Sarah Fatima¹RHC Daultala, Gujar Khan, Rawalpindi, ²MO, RHC Daultala, Gujar Khan, Rawalpindi, ³Yusra Medical and Dental College Islamabad.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:****Objective:** To explore the curve width in untreated Class II subjects with normal and high mandibular plane points.**Study Design:** Cross sectional comparative study.**Place and Duration of Study:** The investigation was led in Jinnah Hospital. Lahore from Oct 2018 to April 2019.**Patients and Methods:** Pretreatment dental throws and cephalograms of skeletal class II patients with complete arrangement of changeless dentition aside from third molars answering to the OPD of Orthodontic office were chosen. Records of 60 patients (30 high point, 30 typical edges) were haphazardly chosen out of the 240 records examined. Intermolar and intercanine widths were estimated in millimeters utilizing advanced calipers. Mandibular plane edge was estimated from cephalometric tracings utilizing the SN Mandibular plane (GoGn SN) point as utilized in Steiner's investigation.**Results:** The mean intermolar width for the ordinary edge bunch was 49.18 ± 2.69 mm and 48.56 ± 4.44 mm for the high point gathering. The mean intercanine width for the ordinary edge bunch was 34.41 ± 2.33 mm and for the high point bunch it was 33.13 ± 2.60 mm. Autonomous t test neglected to demonstrate any huge ($p > 0.05$) contrast in the IMW among ordinary and high edge patients. Anyway a huge ($p < 0.05$) contrast was seen in the intercanine width of the ordinary and high edge gatherings.**Conclusion:** In our examination there was no huge distinction of intermolar width while critical contrast of intercanine width was found among ordinary and high point cases.**Keywords:** Mandibular plane angle, Inter molar width, Inter canine width, skeletal Class II.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Waqar Qamar,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Changes fit as a fiddle of the facial bones is controlled by sutural, cartilaginous, periosteal and endosteal bone renovating. [1] An imperative job in the renovating procedure is played by delicate tissues identifying with the bones and useful needs [1-5]. Variety in curve width is found in people with various facial structures. Curve width of short confronted people is more noteworthy than that of the since quite a while ago confronted people. Since quite a while ago confronted people may give a tight curve. Numerous investigations have demonstrated the impact of jaw muscles on facial structure. Finn [6] announced that most extreme gnawing power in the molar district was more prominent in brachyfacial (short-face) subjects than in dolichofacial (disappointed look) subjects. Proffit et al [7] found that disappointed look grown-ups have fundamentally less occlusal compel amid most extreme exertion, reproduced biting and gulping than do subjects with typical vertical facial measurements.

Clinicians regularly give much consideration to the tendency of the mandibular plane, since it is a noteworthy determinant of the vertical component of a face (long, normal, or short). An individual with a more extreme mandibular plane to cranial base (bigger MP-SN edge) frequently has a long foremost facial tallness, a littler proportion of back to front facial stature, and short mandibular ramus tallness. Then again, an individual with a level mandibular plane (littler MP-SN point) has a short front facial stature, a bigger proportion of back to foremost facial tallness, and a long mandibular ramus stature. [8-11] On the off chance that each individual has an alternate curve width and curve structure, utilizing individualized curve wires as per every patient's pre-

treatment curve structure and width is recommended amid orthodontic treatment to build the solidness of the outcome. In this way the motivation behind this examination was to explore the curve width (intermolar and intercanine remove) in untreated (Class II malocclusion) subjects with normal and high MP-SN edges.

Patients and methods duration:

This examination was led at, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore from Oct 2018 to April 2019. Pretreatment dental throws and cephalograms of skeletal class II patients answering to the OPD of orthodontic office were chosen. Records of just class II patients with complete arrangement of lasting dentition aside from third molars were chosen from the holding up rundown. Patients with a background marked by orthodontic treatment or craniofacial disorder were barred from the investigation. In view of these criteria an aggregate of 60 records (30 high points, 30 typical edges) were haphazardly chosen out of the 240 examined. Utilizing the dental throws, the accompanying estimations were recorded.

* Maxillary intermolar width was the linear measurement between the mesiobuccal cusp tips of the right and left maxillary first molars.

* Maxillary intercanine width was the linear measurement between the tips of the right and left maxillary cuspids.

All intermolar and intercanine widths were estimated in millimeters utilizing advanced calipers. Horizontal cephalometric radiographs were utilized. Mandibular plane point was estimated from cephalometric tracings utilizing the SN Mandibular plane (GoGn SN) edge as utilized in Steiner's examination (Figure).

Figure: Steiner's mandibular plane

Information examination was finished utilizing SPSS

form 14. Autonomous t-test was utilized to look at

the Inter canine and intermolar width between typical edge and high point. A p estimation of < 0.05 was considered factually critical.

RESULTS:

The mean intermolar width for the ordinary edge bunch was 49.18 ± 2.69 mm and 48.56 ± 4.44 mm for the high edge gathering (Table).

Table: Descriptive statics and p values

	Normalangle		Highangle		p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
IMW	49.18	2.69	48.56	4.44	0.51
ICW	34.41	2.33	33.13	2.60	0.048

The thing that matters was irrelevant ($p > 0.05$) The mean intercanine width for the ordinary edge bunch was 34.41 ± 2.33 mm and for the high point bunch it was 33.13 ± 2.60 mm. There was noteworthy contrast in intercanine width of both the gatherings ($p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION:

Our investigation demonstrated no critical distinction of intermolar width while huge contrast of intercanine width was found among ordinary and high edge cases. Entomb canine width diminished with an expansion in the mandibular plane edge. Numerous examinations demonstrate the variety in curve width with the change in mandibular plane point. Christie [12] assessed orthodontic records of 82 white grown-ups (43 ladies, 39 men) with typical untreated impediments and found that short-face men had more prominent maxillary and mandibular widths than ordinary men. Be that as it may, no distinctions in width were found between short-face and typical ladies. They didn't give information on gloomy appearance subjects in light of the fact that the example measure was excessively little (just 4).

Our investigation incorporated the records of 60 patients and a reduction in intercanine width with the expansion in mandibular plane was seen. Anyway our examination did not think about sexual orientation contrasts. Weijs and Hillen [13] and van Sprosen et al [14] found that the cross-sectional zones of the temporalis and masseter muscles connected decidedly with facial width. They recommended that the jaw muscles influence facial development and halfway decide the last facial measurements. Kiliaridis [15] likewise recommended that the expanded stacking of the jaws from masticatory muscle hyperfunction may prompt expanded sutural development and bone pairing, bringing about expanded transversal development of the maxilla and more extensive bone bases for the dental curves. Tsunori et al [16] announced that, when contrasted and normal and disappointed look people, short-face subjects had bigger intermolar widths and more prominent buccal cortical bone thicknesses in the molar region of the mandible. They recommended a conceivable connection between the advancement of the maxillofacial complex in the vertical and transverse measurements and proportions

of expanded strength.

CONCLUSION:

In our examination there was critical contrast of intercanine width among typical and high edge cases. Bury canine width diminished with an expansion in the mandibular plane edge. No huge contrast of intermolar width was watched.

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